

UNDERSTANDING THE FLOW PROPERTIES OF A THERMOPLASTIC-TOUGHENED EPOXY RESIN FILM THROUGH MODEL-BASED ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

In this study, the through-thickness flow characteristics of a thermoplastic-toughened resin film were predicted using a one-dimensional flow model accounting for fabric deformation and time-dependent viscosity changes. The model aims to enhance the flow behaviour of the relatively high-viscous resin by analysing the effect of each processing factor on the fibre wet-out in the infusion process. A parametric study of the processing parameters, heating rate and pressure, and their contribution to the resin flow performance were undertaken in order to optimise the cure cycle for an out-of-autoclave resin film infusion (OoA/RFI) process. This research was undertaken at Carbon Nexus where rapid processing of composite materials is one of the key research themes.

1 INTRODUCTION

Resin film infusion (RFI) of textile preforms is an advanced, cost-efficient process for the manufacture of composite parts with a high potential for automation. Thermoplastic toughened resins have been increasingly applied in composite structures; however their application in infusion processes has been limited as the process viscosity lies in a relatively high viscosity range, where resin flow becomes very limited. One key benefit of through-thickness infusion techniques, such as RFI, is the ability to use highly viscous, toughened resins, as a shorter resin flow distance than those encountered in in-plane liquid resin infusion methods is required to wet out the fibrous preform.

A number of processing parameters, such as temperature, time and pressure, affect the resin flow during resin infusion. Using the knowledge about the resin's rheology and designing a flow-optimised cure cycle rather than the traditional prepreg cure cycle may be one way to enhance the impregnation properties of a toughened resin film. Even though researchers have been active in investigating the temperature-time dependency of a thermoset resin viscosity, only limited research has been undertaken to analyse the effect of each processing factor on the resin flow and fibre wet-out in an infusion process.

In this study, the through-thickness flow characteristics of a thermoplastic-toughened resin film were predicted using a one-dimensional flow model accounting for fabric deformation and time-dependent viscosity changes. The investigation aimed to predict the resin's processability in an out-of-autoclave (OoA) environment and identify the effect of the cure cycle variables and their contribution to the resin flow performance. This work builds on previous research undertaken at Carbon Nexus (Geelong, Australia), where research into carbon fibre, OoA curing and rapid processing of composite materials are strategic research focus areas. The unique research facility allows research on various aspects of carbon fibre production and composite manufacture within one centre.

2 MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL

The resin material used was M18-1(Hexcel, France) resin film. The thermoplastic modified resin film weighed 75g/m² and multiple film layers were stacked beforehand in order to provide the amount of resin required for each respective panel thickness. A debulking cycle was applied after every fourth layer. The composite laminates were made from a biaxial non-crimp (SAERTEX, Germany) carbon fabric (NCF), 256g/m² based on 90/0° and ±45° biaxial layers.

The experimental work was performed utilising the Quickstep™ research plant. This out-of-autoclave process uses a liquid as the heating medium, which allows processing at higher heating and cooling rates compared to an autoclave or oven. Throughout the curing process the panel temperature and process pressure were recorded. The laminates were cured under a vacuum bag pressure of -97kPa and additional 10kPa provided by the Quickstep™ pressure chambers.

Figure 1: a) Resin film, b) bi-axial NCF and c) vacuum bag arrangement

3 MODEL APPROACH

3.1 Flow model

The implementation of a process model in this investigation intended to predict the transverse flow of the toughened resin through the dry fibre preform dependent on a number of the processing parameters. The hybrid one-dimensional process model, which predicts the transverse flow through a fibre preform, was supported by two submodels describing the chemo-rheology and fibre compaction.

Fibre compaction tests were carried out on the biaxial NCF (SAERTEX, Germany). The relationship between preform deformation under applied load was described following the power law in Equation (1), where V_f is the fibre volume fraction, P_c the compaction pressure acting on the fibre with $d=11.34$ and $c=1.41 \cdot 10^8$.

$$V_f = \frac{P_c}{c}^{\frac{1}{d}} \quad (1)$$

The corresponding changes in permeability were obtained using Equation (2), where K_z the through-thickness preform permeability with $a=5.85 \cdot 10^{-14}$ and $b=-3.74$.

$$K_z = a \cdot \left(\frac{P_c}{c}\right)^{\frac{b}{d}} \quad (2)$$

The resin velocity at the flow front is described by Darcy's law of flow through porous media by differentiation of Equation (3) and substitution of P_c and K at the flow front:

$$\frac{dz}{dt} = \left[\frac{1}{\eta} \frac{K_z}{(1 - V_f)} \frac{\partial P_c}{\partial z} \right]_{z=h} \quad (3)$$

The time- and temperature-dependent resin flow front, h , was predicted by applying an analytical model solution proposed by Park and Saouab [1] differentiating Equation (3) at the flow front ($z=h$). The model provides a fully analytical solution for one-dimensional flow in the RFI process and considers the pressure distribution over the laminate thickness and fibre volume fraction distribution. However, it does not take time-dependent viscosity changes into account, which is required when applying a model to

cure cycle optimisation. To apply the model proposed by Park and Saouab [1] for temperature cure cycle optimisation, the solution for Equation (3) suggested by the authors needed to be modified. In order to allow for time-dependent viscosity changes, Equation (4) was solved numerically using a fourth order Runge-Kutta method. The resulting hybrid one-dimensional process model is a useful tool for flow prediction under non-isothermal conditions, determination of infiltration time and whether complete infiltration can be achieved before the resin gels.

3.2 Chemo-rheology model

The resin kinetics and chemo-rheology parameter of the M18-1 resin film, determined in a separate study [2], were used to predict the resin viscosity under non-isothermal cure conditions in the RFI process. The autocatalytic model [3] in Equation (4) was used to describe the cure kinetics of PEI toughened epoxy/amine resin system,

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = \frac{(k_1 + k_2 a^m)(1 - \alpha)^n}{1 + \exp[C(a - a_c)]} \quad (4)$$

where k_1 and k_2 are specific rate constants related to the primary and secondary amine-epoxy reaction, the parameter of diffusion control $C=38$ and $a_c=0.036 \cdot T - 0.722$ the critical degree of conversion, at which point the reaction becomes controlled by diffusion. The overall reaction order $m=-0.0063 \cdot T + 4.291$ and $n=-0.0035 \cdot T + 4.041$ are temperature dependent.

$$k_i = A_i \exp\left(\frac{-E_i}{RT}\right), \quad i=1,2 \quad (5)$$

The temperature dependence of the rate constants is given by the Arrhenius expressions in Equation (5), where $A_1=86855s^{-1}$ and $A_2=192s^{-1}$ are the pre-exponential factors, $E_1=72.46kJ/mol$ and $E_2=38.57kJ/mol$ the activation energy for the primary or secondary amine-epoxy reaction, R is the universal gas constant and T the reaction temperature. A viscosity model by Castro-Macosko [29] that describes changes in viscosity related the occurrence of chemical reactions was used to calculate the time-dependent viscosity,

$$\eta = \eta_{\infty} \exp\left(\frac{\Delta E \eta}{RT}\right) \left[\frac{\alpha_g}{(\alpha_g - \alpha)} \right]^{(A+B\alpha)} \quad (6)$$

with a pre-exponential factor $\eta_{\infty}=3.57 \cdot 10^{10}$ Pas and an activation energy value $\Delta E \eta=78918$ kJ/mol the degree of cure at gelation, $\alpha_{gel}=0.45$ and temperature dependent fitting parameters $A=-0.094 \cdot T + 47.5$ and $B=0.044 \cdot T - 20$. Combining Equations (4) and (6) the resin viscosity can be predicted for any given temperature profile the resin undergoes during the RFI manufacture of composite parts. The model output is the time and temperature dependent resin viscosity, which will be fed into the flow model.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Experimental Validation

Before quantifying the effect of processing parameters on the infusion properties using the proposed model approach, the one-dimensional flow model was experimentally validated. In order to track the change in resin viscosity during the cure process, a monitoring system based on DC-resistance was developed. The resin detection sensors based on DC-resistance technique were employed to validate not only the predicted infusion height, but also the time dependent flow progression over the laminate thickness. The sensor was made from a thin 0.2mm T-type thermocouple wire with disconnected ends held in place 1mm apart as presented in Figure 2. The insulation material was removed to a distance of 1mm from the wire end. The exposed thermocouple wire ends were placed between dry NCF layers. At the time the resin arrives and contacts the sensor, the electrical circuit is closed resulting in a signal response. To avoid false resistance measurements due to contact with the conductive carbon fibres, the resin detection sensors were embedded in glass fibre patches.

Figure 2: a) DC-resistance sensor geometry and b) and distribution within the carbon fibre laminate (horizontal lines indicate biaxial plies of NCF)

A dry fibre preform, 12 plies thick, was infiltrated with M18-1 resin under vacuum using the RFI technique. A vacuum pressure of 97kPa and an additional 10kPa process pressure were applied to the laminate during the cure cycle. The laminate was heated in the QuickstepTM process at 10°C/min to 110°C, held for 20min and further heated to 180°C for final cure.

The predicted flow front advancement with consideration of time-dependent viscosity changes are compared to experimental data, such as resin flow paths captured by resin detection sensors. Degree of cure and resin viscosity of the resin film were calculated based on the temperature-time profiles monitored during the experiment, using Equation (6). Figure 3 shows the flow model validation results including the predicted and experimentally measured time-dependent flow front as well as the sensor response for resin detection, where each peak represents one incoming sensor signal.

Figure 3: a) Viscosity profile during model validation tests and, b) DC-Resistance sensor response and modelled flow front evolution through the preform as a function of time.

The flow behaviour can be described by a slow flow ramp up to the second ramp at about 22min, from which point the resin is drawn through the laminate at a much higher rate. The resin started to cure at the introduction of the second heating ramp and caused the resin viscosity to rise after a total of 26min. Due to the advancement in cure the flow decelerated until it fully stagnated 43min throughout the cure cycle, the time at which 45% cure was reached. When compared with the experimental data, the predicted flow progression shows excellent agreement. When comparing the results above, one can conclude that the model assumptions are valid and can be employed in one-dimensional flow prediction in the OoA/RFI cure cycle optimisation.

5 MODELLING RESULTS

5.1 Effect of Processing Parameters

An analysis on the effect of pressure on resin flow was performed for a typical cure cycle with a heating rate of 2.5°C/min up to 110°C, a first dwell time of 60min, followed by another ramp of 10°C/min to a final dwell of 180°C. For the matter of manufacturing cost-saving, OoA resin infusion is usually performed under low external pressure. However, to understand the relationship and impact of pressure on the RFI process using a thermoplastic toughened resin film, a pressure range from 100kPa as applied during vacuum-only infusion to 500kPa as applied in an autoclave process was included in the investigation.

The fibre stack consists of 10 plies of biaxial NCF. Flow front advancement, resin film height and the overall laminate thickness as a function of pressure P_{ext} were calculated following the model described above, and graphed in Figure 4. High process pressures are shown to have a significant effect on infiltration time and flow distance. Compared to a vacuum-only process with 100kPa bag pressure, a 22% enhancement of flow distance can be achieved for 200kPa and 67% with a processing pressure of 500kPa. The graph also indicates, that the extent of effect ceases with increasing pressure. From Figure 4 it can be seen that the initial resin film thickness is a function of pressure applied. The resin film height diminishes over time with flow front progression by filling the fibre porosity. To assure successful infiltration with a resulting high fibre volume content and avoid a resin rich laminate surface on the tool side, the resin film mass should equal zero by the time the flow front reaches the top of the laminate as indicated by the curve crossing point (circled markers) for flow front advancement and total laminate height. The graph shows that in case of a low pressure along with the heating rate of 2.5C/min the resin will not reach the top of the laminate, which will result in a dry laminate surface.

Figure 4: Comparison of flow front enhancement and total laminate thickness (resin + 10 plies biaxial of NCF) and reduction of resin film height in an RFI process

Although the infiltration time saving by applying additional pressure (Figure 4) is significant, it may not shorten the manufacturing cure cycle as the degree of cure is assumed to be the same over time for all cases of pressure applied. Therefore, the same length of cure cycle is required to fully cure the resin matrix. However, shorter infiltration times assist complete wet-out before resin gelation occurs, which overcomes the limits imposed by the resin kinetics.

In order to shorten the cure cycle time, faster heating rates may be employed. Figure 5 illustrates the flow front progression through a 10ply laminate for heating rates of 2.5, 5 and 10°C/min and 100kPa pressure from which an improvement in flow performance for the higher heating rate can be observed. Although the degree of cure advances at a slower rate with 2.5°C/min, the viscosity remains at higher values leading to an incomplete fibre wet-out (Figure 5b). The remaining resin will be left on the tool side of the part resulting in a resin rich surface and local stress within the part due to inhomogeneous resin distribution. With the higher heating rate, the flow distance for this cure cycle was extended by 6.5% with 5°C/min and 8.2% with 10°C/min assuring complete infiltration.

Figure 5: Comparison of different heating rates and their effect on a) degree of cure and viscosity as a function of time and b) infusion behaviour, and resin film consumption

When comparing the RFI infiltration time using various heating rates, a time saving of about 30% was achieved using a high heating rate of 10°C/min and 20% with 5°C/min when compared to a slow heating rate of 2.5°C/min.

The above presented case studies are only examples that highlight the transparency of the model and its capability to reproduce the flow of the applied thermoplastic-toughened resin film through the NCF and its response to changes in process variables.

9 CONCLUSIONS

The through-thickness flow characteristics of the thermoplastic-toughened resin system M18-1 in an OoA/RFI process was successfully predicted by applying a one-dimensional resin flow model. An analytical flow model proposed by Park and Saouab [1] was extended numerically to allow for a viscosity-time dependency, a very important variable in the cure cycle optimisation. Experimental verification of the calculated data supported the validity of the flow model.

High process pressures were found to have a positive effect on infiltration time and flow distance. The relationship between flow distance and pressure is nonlinear, with decreasing flow improvements for higher pressures. The analysis of the effect of heating rate on the resin matrix flow demonstrated that an increase in heating rate lowers the process viscosity, which ultimately contributes to flow. However the effect was rather small when compared to pressure.

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